

A NOTE ON q -ANALOGUE OF SÁNDOR'S FUNCTIONS

by

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Dedicated to Sun-Yi Park on 90th birthday

ABSTRACT

The additive analogues of Pseudo-Smarandache, Smarandache-simple functions and their duals have been recently studied by J. Sándor. In this note, we obtain q -analogues of Sándor's theorems [6].

Keywords and Phrases: q -gamma function, Pseudo-Smarandache function, Smarandache-simple function, Asymtotic formula.

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1 Introduction

The additive analogues of Smarandache functions S and S_* have been introduced by Sándor [5] as follows:

$$S(x) = \min\{m \in N : x \leq m!\}, \quad x \in (1, \infty),$$

and

$$S_*(x) = \max\{m \in N : m! \leq x\}, \quad x \in [1, \infty).$$

He has studied many important properties of S_* relating to continuity, differentiability and Riemann integrability and also proved the following theorems:

Theorem 1.1

$$S_*(x) \sim \frac{\log x}{\log \log x} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Theorem 1.2 The series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(S_*(n))^\alpha}$$

is convergent for $\alpha > 1$ and divergent for $\alpha \leq 1$.

In [1], Adiga and Kim have obtained generalizations of Theorems 1.1 and 1.2 by the use of Euler's gamma function. Recently Adiga-Kim-Somashekara-Fathima [2] have established a q -analogues of these results on employing the q -analogue of Stirling's formula. In [6], Sándor defined the additive analogues of Pseudo-Smarandache, Smarandache-simple functions and their duals as follows:

$$Z(x) = \min \left\{ m \in N : x \leq \frac{m(m+1)}{2} \right\}, \quad x \in (0, \infty),$$

$$Z_*(x) = \max \left\{ m \in N : \frac{m(m+1)}{2} \leq x \right\}, \quad x \in [1, \infty),$$

$$P(x) = \min\{m \in N : p^x \leq m!\}, \quad p > 1, x \in (0, \infty),$$

and

$$P_*(x) = \max\{m \in N : m! \leq p^x\}, \quad p > 1, x \in [1, \infty).$$

He has also proved the following theorems:

Theorem 1.3

$$Z_*(x) \sim \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{8x+1} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Theorem 1.4 The series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(Z_*(n))^\alpha}$$

is convergent for $\alpha > 2$ and divergent for $\alpha \leq 2$. The series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(Z_*(n))^\alpha}$$

is convergent for all $\alpha > 0$.

Theorem 1.5

$$\log P_*(x) \sim \log x \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Theorem 1.6 The series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{\log \log n}{\log P_*(n)} \right)^\alpha$$

is convergent for $\alpha > 1$ and divergent for $\alpha \leq 1$.

The main purpose of this note is to obtain q -analogues of Sándor's Theorems 1.3 and 1.5. In what follows, we make use of the following notations and definitions. F. H. Jackson defined a q -analogue of the gamma function which extends the q -factorial

$$(n!)_q = 1(1+q)(1+q+q^2) \cdots (1+q+q^2+\cdots+q^{n-1}), \quad \text{cf [3]},$$

which becomes the ordinary factorial as $q \rightarrow 1$. He defined the q -analogue of

the gamma function as

$$\Gamma_q(x) = \frac{(q; q)_\infty}{(q^x; q)_\infty} (1 - q)^{1-x}, \quad 0 < q < 1,$$

and

$$\Gamma_q(x) = \frac{(q^{-1}; q^{-1})_\infty}{(q^{-x}; q^{-1})_\infty} (q - 1)^{1-x} q^{\binom{x}{2}}, \quad q > 1,$$

where

$$(a; q)_\infty = \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - aq^n).$$

It is well known that $\Gamma_q(x) \rightarrow \Gamma(x)$ as $q \rightarrow 1$, where $\Gamma(x)$ is the ordinary gamma function.

2 Main Theorems

We now define the q -analogues of Z and Z_* as follows:

$$Z_q(x) = \min \left\{ \frac{1 - q^m}{1 - q} : x \leq \frac{\Gamma_q(m+2)}{2\Gamma_q(m)} \right\}, \quad m \in N, x \in (0, \infty),$$

and

$$Z_q^*(x) = \max \left\{ \frac{1 - q^m}{1 - q} : \frac{\Gamma_q(m+2)}{2\Gamma_q(m)} \leq x \right\}, \quad m \in N, x \in \left[\frac{\Gamma_q(3)}{2\Gamma_q(1)}, \infty \right),$$

where $0 < q < 1$. Clearly, $Z_q(x) \rightarrow Z(x)$ and $Z_q^*(x) \rightarrow Z_*(x)$ as $q \rightarrow 1^-$. From the definitions of Z_q and Z_q^* , it is clear that

$$Z_q(x) = \left[\begin{array}{ll} 1, & \text{if } x \in \left(0, \frac{\Gamma_q(3)}{2\Gamma_q(1)} \right] \\ \frac{1 - q^m}{1 - q}, & \text{if } x \in \left(\frac{\Gamma_q(m+1)}{2\Gamma_q(m-1)}, \frac{\Gamma_q(m+2)}{2\Gamma_q(m)} \right], m \geq 2, \end{array} \right] \quad (2.1)$$

and

$$Z_q^*(x) = \frac{1 - q^m}{1 - q} \quad \text{if } x \in \left[\frac{\Gamma_q(m+2)}{2\Gamma_q(m)}, \frac{\Gamma_q(m+3)}{2\Gamma_q(m+1)} \right). \quad (2.2)$$

Since

$$\frac{1 - q^{m-1}}{1 - q} \leq \frac{1 - q^m}{1 - q} = \frac{1 - q^{m-1}}{1 - q} + q^{m-1} \leq \frac{1 - q^{m-1}}{1 - q} + 1,$$

(2.1) and (2.2) imply that for $x \geq \frac{\Gamma_q(3)}{2\Gamma_q(1)}$,

$$Z_q^*(x) \leq Z_q(x) \leq Z_q^*(x) + 1.$$

Hence it suffices to study the function Z_q^* . We now prove our main theorems.

Theorem 2.1 If $0 < q < 1$, then

$$\frac{\sqrt{1 + 8xq} - (1 + 2q)}{2q^2} < Z_q^*(x) \leq \frac{\sqrt{1 + 8xq} - 1}{2q}, \quad x \geq \frac{\Gamma_q(3)}{2\Gamma_q(1)}.$$

Proof. If

$$\frac{\Gamma_q(k+2)}{2\Gamma_q(k)} \leq x < \frac{\Gamma_q(k+3)}{2\Gamma_q(k+1)}, \quad (2.3)$$

then

$$Z_q^*(x) = \frac{1 - q^k}{1 - q}$$

and

$$(1 - q^k)(1 - q^{k+1}) - 2x(1 - q)^2 \leq 0 < (1 - q^{k+1})(1 - q^{k+2}) - 2x(1 - q)^2. \quad (2.4)$$

Consider the functions f and g defined by

$$f(y) = (1 - y)(1 - yq) - 2x(1 - q)^2$$

and

$$g(y) = (1 - yq)(1 - yq^2) - 2x(1 - q)^2.$$

Note that f is monotonically decreasing for $y \leq \frac{1+q}{2q}$ and g is strictly decreasing for $y < \frac{1+q}{2q^2}$. Also $f(y_1) = 0 = g(y_2)$ where

$$y_1 = \frac{(1 + q) - (1 - q)\sqrt{1 + 8xq}}{2q},$$

$$y_2 = \frac{(q + q^2) - q(1 - q)\sqrt{1 + 8xq}}{2q^3}.$$

Since $y_1 < \frac{1+q}{2q}$, $y_2 < \frac{1+q}{2q^2}$ and $q^k < \frac{1+q}{2q} < \frac{1+q}{2q^2}$, from (2.4), it follows that

$$f(q^k) \leq f(y_1) = 0 = g(y_2) < g(q^k).$$

Thus $y_1 \leq q^k < y_2$ and hence

$$\frac{1 - y_2}{1 - q} < \frac{1 - q^k}{1 - q} \leq \frac{1 - y_1}{1 - q}.$$

i.e.

$$\frac{\sqrt{1 + 8xq} - (1 + 2q)}{2q^2} < Z_q^*(x) \leq \frac{\sqrt{1 + 8xq} - 1}{2q}.$$

This completes the proof.

Remark. Letting $q \rightarrow 1^-$ in the above theorem, we obtain Sándor's Theorem 1.3.

We define the q -analogues of P and P_* as follows:

$$P_q(x) = \min\{m \in N : p^x \leq \Gamma_q(m + 1)\}, \quad p > 1, x \in (0, \infty),$$

and

$$P_q^*(x) = \max\{m \in N : \Gamma_q(m+1) \leq p^x\}, \quad p > 1, x \in [1, \infty),$$

where $0 < q < 1$. Clearly, $P_q(x) \rightarrow P(x)$ and $P_q^*(x) \rightarrow P_*(x)$ as $q \rightarrow 1^-$. From the definitions of P_q and P_q^* , we have

$$P_q^*(x) \leq P_q(x) \leq P_q^*(x) + 1.$$

Hence it is enough to study the function P_q^* .

Theorem 2.2 If $0 < q < 1$, then

$$P_*(x) \sim \frac{x \log p}{\log\left(\frac{1}{1-q}\right)} \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Proof. If $\Gamma_q(n+1) \leq p^x < \Gamma_q(n+2)$, then

$$P_q^*(x) = n$$

and

$$\log \Gamma_q(n+1) \leq \log p^x < \log \Gamma_q(n+2). \quad (2.5)$$

But by the q -analogue of Stirling's formula established by Moak [4], we have

$$\log \Gamma_q(n+1) \sim \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \log \left(\frac{q^{n+1} - 1}{q - 1}\right) \sim n \log \left(\frac{1}{1-q}\right). \quad (2.6)$$

Dividing (2.5) throughout by $n \log\left(\frac{1}{1-q}\right)$, we obtain

$$\frac{\log \Gamma_q(n+1)}{n \log\left(\frac{1}{1-q}\right)} \leq \frac{x \log p}{P_q^*(x) \log\left(\frac{1}{1-q}\right)} < \frac{\log \Gamma_q(n+2)}{n \log\left(\frac{1}{1-q}\right)}. \quad (2.7)$$

Using (2.6) in (2.7), we deduce

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x \log p}{P_q^*(x) \log\left(\frac{1}{1-q}\right)} = 1.$$

This completes the proof.

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